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**THE ROLE OF GAMES IN FOSTERING LANGUAGE LEARNING
AND SELF-REGULATION IN HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS:
STRATEGIES FOR PROMOTING METACOGNITIVE AWARENESS**

Qadamboyeva Guli

Student of Uzbekistan State World Languages University

English philology faculty

Email: gulipink9@gmail.com

Abstract. *In today's education, game-based learning is considered an effective tool in language teaching. This article examines how games improve high school students' language learning strategies, increase their self-regulation skills, and provide metacognitive awareness. Because of the dynamic structure of games, students both have fun and actively participate in the learning process. Games offer effective strategies for improving language skills, while also helping students realize their metacognitive processes. This study offers suggestions to teachers on the use of games in education and reveals the potential of game-based applications in language learning.*

Keywords. *Language learning, game-based learning, self-regulation, metacognitive awareness, high school students, learning strategies.*

Introduction. Language learning is not just about acquiring knowledge, it also requires practice, interaction and self-regulation. Games play an important role in supporting these processes. High school students are generally in the process of developing their social and cognitive skills, and it is known that games increase intrinsic motivation and make the learning process more fun.

The role of games in language learning:

Participation and motivation: Games increase students' participation in the lesson and make the learning process more fun. While traditional teaching methods can often be passive learning, games make students active. Especially competitive and cooperative games make students put more effort into developing their language skills. Research shows that game-based learning increases students' desire to learn and encourages their active participation. **Contextual learning:** Games facilitate understanding of vocabulary and grammatical structures by presenting language learning in context. For example, simulation games or role-playing activities give students the chance to use language in real-life scenarios. This contextual learning helps students develop language skills more permanently.

Instant feedback: games support the learning process by providing instant feedback to players. Students can immediately see the mistakes they make in the game and develop strategies to correct them. This can lead to self-assessment. For instance, when a student is immediately shown a word or grammar structure that they have used incorrectly, the student has the opportunity to make an effort to correct the error. The instant feedback is important for developing self-assessment skills.

Social interaction: Games play a crucial role in increasing social interaction. When students play games that require them to communicate by working in groups, they can increase their language practice and develop their social skills.

Collaborative games help students develop strategies together, use language and strengthen their social skills. These types of games provide opportunities to practice language learning in a social context, making learning more effective.

Self-regulation is the ability of individuals to manage their own learning processes. Through play, students can set goals, monitor their progress, and evaluate their own learning processes. Metacognitive awareness is the capacity of students to understand and evaluate their thought processes. Games help students develop strategy development and choice-making skills. Post-game reflective activities allow students to analyze which learning strategies were successful. In this way, students become more independent and effective learners.

Strategies to support game-based learning includes goal-setting, feedback mechanisms, reflective practices, various game formats. In goal-setting, students should be encouraged to determine what they want to achieve before the game. These goals provide a reference point for them to evaluate their progress during the game. Feedback mechanisms in games should be used to monitor student performance. Instant feedback helps students gain insights into areas where they need to improve further. Reflective practices are important for students to have the opportunity to think and reflect after the game. In this context, class discussions and reflective writing activities will be useful for students to evaluate their experiences. It is recommended that instructors use a variety of game types that appeal to students' different learning styles. This increases engagement for all students and allows for the development of different skills along the way.

Conclusion. Games play a critical role in improving the language learning process of high school students and increasing their self-regulation skills. While making language learning fun, they also have the potential to increase students' metacognitive awareness. Educators should integrate game-based strategies into their lessons to create a more interactive and motivating learning environment. In

this way, students' language learning processes will become more fun and productive.

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MODERN TRENDS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Qadamboyeva Nilufar

Uzbekistan State University of World Languages

English Philology Faculty

niluzaqwsx@gmail.com

***Abstract.** Through this article, the author explores current trends of teaching and learning foreign languages in terms of teaching methods, approaches, evaluation, assignments, educational tools thanks to new developments in technology in our globalized era.*

***Keywords.** Educational technology, innovation, creativity, critical thinking, motivating students, proficiency.*